

Untapped Potential of Buddhist Tourism in West Bengal

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Abstract

The value of Buddhist tourism in respect of pilgrimage cum cultural tourism as well as archaeo-heritage tourism cannot be exaggerated. Quite in line with the importance that UNWTO confers on heritage and cultural tourism with respect to educating the common people about the value of the tangible and non-tangible heritage left by our ancestors, conservation of that heritage, creating a respectful dialogue between the guest and the host communities and thus promoting peace and mutual understanding among different cultures of the world, the Government of India is taking various steps to utilise the rich resources of the Buddhist heritage in our country. But it is quite unfortunate that West Bengal, despite being a seat of Buddhist religion and educational centres in the past, especially in the Buddhist Pala period, is out of the entire endeavour of the Government of India. In this essay an attempt has been made to assess the potential of Buddhist tourism in West Bengal, identify the limitations and challenges holding it back, and find some suggestions and recommendations that are both practicable and sustainable to overcome those impediments.

Key Words: Buddhist tourism, Pilgrimage tourism, Cultural tourism, Archaeo-heritage tourism, Monastic tourism, Himalayan Buddhism.

Introduction:

India has been the cradle of Buddhism since the birth of the Buddha 2500 years ago. Despite the ups and downs in the history of Buddhism in India it has always been the magnificent storehouse of the Buddhist heritage and culture, both in terms of tangible and intangible forms of it, making the country a potential attraction in view of Buddhist tourism thriving throughout the South and South-East Asian countries. As per the data provided by the NITI Aayog under the Government of India, the foreign tourist footfall in the Buddhist destinations share only 6.06% of the total number of FTVs (Foreign Tourist Visitors) to all states/UTs (which is 28.87 million) in 2018. The data also shows that the percentage of the foreigners visiting the Buddhist destinations has sharply declined in 2018 as compared with the 6.51% in 2016. Considering the immense contribution that the sector of tourism makes to the overall economic health of the country (comprising 8.8% of the total employment, 5.8% of the total exports and 6.9% of the country's GDP in 2019) (<https://www.niti.gov.in>) the Government of India has taken a number of initiatives like Swadesh Darshan Scheme under which 5 projects with an estimated cost of Rs 325.53 crore have been allotted for the development works of the Buddhist Circuit involving the six states of Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Orissa, Gujarat, and Andhra Pradesh, the Pilgrimage Rejuvenation and Spiritual Heritage Augmentation Drive (PRASHAD) scheme under which Rs 44.19 crore has been sanctioned for three projects including the restoration and development works of the Buddhist structures and light and sound shows at different Buddhist locations and theme parks (source: <https://pib.gov.in>).

In spite of the fact that West Bengal, an adjacent state of Bihar and Orissa having a history of three hundred years of Buddhist Pala dynasty, housing sites like Srivandakavihara, famously known as Moghalmari Buddha Vihara, Nandadirghivihara at Jagjivanpur, the ancient port of Tamralipta, and the home of the different sects of Himalayan Buddhism, still being practiced by thousands of Buddhists in the northern districts of the state, and thus being a potential repository of Buddhist pilgrimage tourism, heritage tourism and archaeo-tourism has unfortunately remained outside of this grand vista of promotion of Buddhist tourism in our country. The objective of this paper is to

undergo a thorough study examining the possibility of West Bengal in attracting domestic as well as overseas tourists interested in exploring the Buddhist sites, the challenges and limitations to that end and finding some suggestions which are both practicable and sustainable in view of the present resources and advantages that are already in hand. We will accordingly divide our study in three sections, namely, (1) Potential of Buddhist Tourism in West Bengal, (2) Limitations and Challenges and (3) Recommendations and Suggestions.

(1) Potential of Buddhist Tourism in West Bengal

As per the data provided by the International Passenger Survey of India conducted by the Government of India (2006) in respect to motivation of the tourists, cultural diversity plays the most significant role in the influx of highest number of tourists (56%) followed by 'other factors' (25%), making religious places and heritage (19%) the lowest among the factors that motivate the tourists. In respect to site seeing category, while 43% tourists are attracted to the landscape and natural beauty, 34% and 13% of them are interested in visiting monuments and museums or art galleries respectively (<https://www.slideshare.net>). If we combine these two statistical data, it comes out that apart from the attraction of natural landscape a large number of tourists are drawn towards the tangible (monuments etc.) and intangible (cultural traditions) heritage of the country. Although pilgrimage or religious tourism is meant especially for believers in specific faith, religion being a part and parcel of the cultural life of a community, it does not exclude the secular crowd either. It is more so when it comes to the serene yet colourful and spectacular religious festivals and rites that is a trademark of Buddhist monasteries situated in hilly areas of North Bengal. So, when we talk of Buddhist pilgrimage tourism in West Bengal, the cultural aspect of heritage tourism is implied in it. Buddhist tourism is, therefore, something that covers almost all the features of motivational factors that may ignite the interests of tourists.

The uniqueness of Buddhist tourism in West Bengal is that it has all the potentials discussed above to showcase itself as a perfect destination for the tourists. On the one hand, it houses monasteries or Buddhist temples where ritualistic worship is actively practiced making these as potent destinations for religious or pilgrimage tourism cum cultural tourism, on the other, it has sites which are rich in historical value and may, therefore, be precious attractions to promote archaeological tourism. With this consideration we will divide this section into two broad segments. In the first section we will discuss the potential of religious or pilgrimage tourism as a part of cultural tourism with special focus on North Bengal as the seat of the Himalayan Buddhism prospering with its various branches and schools and in the second section we will highlight the potential of archaeological tourism as a part of heritage tourism as may be fathomed from a good number of excavated historical sites reminiscent of a glorious past replete with Buddhist monastic centres as described by the Chinese pilgrims cum scholars of 4th to 7th centuries AD.

(a) Pilgrimage cum religio-cultural tourism:

According to the definition adopted by the UN Tourism General Assembly at its 22nd session held in 2017, cultural tourism is “A type of tourism activity in which the visitor’s essential motivation is to learn, discover, experience and consume the tangible and intangible cultural attractions/products in a tourism destination. These attractions/products relate to a set of distinctive material, intellectual, spiritual and emotional features of a society that encompasses arts and architecture, historical and cultural heritage, culinary heritage, literature, music, creative industries and the living cultures with their lifestyles, value systems, beliefs and traditions.” (<https://www.unwto.org>). Anyone who is familiar with the vibes of the district of Darjeeling will instantly identify it as a peculiar example of the above-mentioned features that comprise a model of cultural tourism. The monastic tourism characteristic particularly of this district along with some other like Jalpaiguri and Kolkata is more ethnic in nature rather than sacred. It has a distinctive feature quite different from other Buddhist pilgrimages of the country like Bodhgaya, Rajgir,

Kushinagar etc. which are associated with the Buddha's life and are thus holy places of worship for all the Buddhists across the globe. The monasteries, called 'Gompas' by the locals of Darjeeling, on the contrary, are places of interest for the secular and non-Buddhists as well. It is not to say that the non-Buddhists do not visit the places famous for the Buddha's life events. Buddhism has a universal appeal and one does not have to be a Buddhist to appreciate the messages of the Buddha or pay homage to Him. But there is a clear difference between the ambiances of the North Bengal monasteries and that of other holy places of Buddhism located mainly in Bihar and Uttar Pradesh. While the former is dropped in by people from all walks of life, it is only a special crowd, largely an informed kind of people that pay a visit to the latter. Again, it is not to say that the monasteries in North Bengal are less valuable in respect to spiritual and religious gravity. What we are trying to indicate is that while the Buddhist temples in other states comprise mainly the pilgrimage or religious tourism in the true sense of the term, the monastic tourism popular in North Bengal are prone to cultural tourism as a whole with its very special ethnicity including lifestyle, festivals, culinary, attires and the like, of which pilgrimage and religious tourism is a significant part.

This distinctiveness is an integral part of the Himalayan or Tibetan Buddhism practiced here. It is quite different from the Buddhist practices largely followed by the Buddhists of the plain land. The connection of Darjeeling with Tibet and Tibetan Buddhism dates back prior to its acquisition by the East India Company in 1835 when it formed a part of Sikkim. The state religion of Sikkim was Vajrayana Buddhism under the Chogyal, the first of whom, Phuntsog Namgyal was a descendant of the Tibetan prince, Khye Bumsa. Darjeeling derived its name itself from two Tibetan words, 'dorje' and 'ling' implying 'thunderbolt' and 'land' respectively. It is, therefore, called 'the land of thunderbolt' (<https://darjeeling.gov.in>). Different schools of Tibetan Buddhism are practiced in different monasteries of Darjeeling. Let us take a quick look on the major monasteries that have the maximum numbers of footfall in Darjeeling.

Ghoom Monastery: Founded in the second half of the 19th century by Sherab Gyatso of Gelug school or the 'yellow hat' sect of Buddhism, the Ghoom monastery or the YigaChoeling monastery is one of the most popular monasteries in Darjeeling. Situated at an altitude of around 8000 feet, it gives a picturesque and serene view of its surrounding landscape. The attraction of the monastery is the magnificent statue of the Maitreya Buddha. The 15 feet high statue containing gold and precious stones is said to be originally made with clay in Tibet.

Japanese Peace Pagoda: Situated at the Jalapahar slopes of the hills, it was built by NichidatsuFujii in the recent past. He was a Japanese monk of the Nipponzan-Myohoji Buddhist order. This pagoda is an embodiment of the eternal messages of peace and harmony.

Samten Choeling Monastery: 1 km away from the YigaChoeling monastery there is the Samten Choeling monastery, which is often confused with the original Ghoom monastery or the Yiga Choeling monastery as mentioned above. It was founded by Lama Sherab Gyatso in 1875, 25 years after the Yiga Choeling monastery was built. This is also a house of monks following Gelug order of Buddhism. It is located some 7 km away from Darjeeling on Hill Cart Road. Here there is a massive 26 feet long statue of Buddha and a rich collection of Buddhist manuscripts. The visitors may join the prayer and meditation and have coffee or tea with some vegetarian snacks at the café inside the monastery premise.

Dali Monastery: Dali Monastery, only a few km away from Darjeeling is a large monastery which houses around 200 Lamas of the Kagyupa Tibetan Buddhist sect. A hall comprising massive golden Tibetan prayer wheels is the chief attraction of this monastery.

Bhutia Busti Monastery: This monastery located at Bhutia Busti belongs to the Red Sect Lamas. It was a branch of Nyingma sect's monastery in Sikkim, this monastery was rebuilt following the Tibetan and Sikkimese architectural pattern after it was relocated in its present location. Among

the rich collection of Buddhist manuscripts an original copy of the “Book of Dead” is worth mentioning.

Mag-Dhog Yolmowa Monastery: This monastery is famous as “Aloobari monastery” deriving its name from the locality in which it is situated. Since the construction work of this monastery began in 1914, the year the World War I started, under the supervision of Sri Sangay Lama, the spiritual abbot of the Yolmo group of people hailing from Nepal, it was so named. The monastery is a symbol of world peace and brotherhood. About 4 km away from the Darjeeling town it is located on the Old Military Road. The serenity and tranquility of this temple is a great attraction for the tourists.

Geden Tharpa Choling Monastery: This monastery is located on Bapai Road at Tirpai in Kalimpong. Founded by Domo Geshe Rinpoche NgawangKalsang in 1912 on request of the locals of Kalimpong, this Gelugpa monastery is directly run by the Dalai Lama Administration at present. It has a monastic school meant for training the young Tibetan monks in exile. The monastery also holds classes on Sunday for the laity to impart Dharma education to them.

Bokar Ngedon Chokhor Ling Monastery: A two hours’ drive from Darjeeling takes one to this monastery situated at Mirik. It was inaugurated in 1986 by KyabjeBokar Rinpoche, a renowned meditation master of the Kagyu school, including the Kalachakra retreat centre, assembly hall and monks’ quarters. It has been conducting an annual seminar for foreign students since 1992. In the words of Rinpoche, “The very foundation of genuine study, reflection, and meditation, that which nourishes authentic explication, debate, and composition, is none other than pure ethical discipline. So in order to sustain these noble teachings of the Buddha we undertake such projects.” (<https://www.bokarmonastery.org>). Visitors including students find this place to be a tranquil place to have a stunning look of the entire Mirik.

Tamang Buddhist Monastery: This monastery located also at Mirik has an exquisite collection of art works decorating the walls and travelers with an interest in art and architecture will find it worth visiting. The wonderful view of Kanchenjunga peak from this spot is also a bonus for the tourists.

Almost all the monasteries have a wide collection of Buddhist scriptures, paintings and thangka. The festival of Tibetan new year called Losar is celebrated on different dates of February and March with great enthusiasm and the monasteries are decorated with vibrant flags. The Cham Dance performed by the Buddhist monks wearing their traditional attire and colorful masks is a special thing to enjoy and cherish the diverse ethnic culture of our state. Among other major festivals mention may be made of Saga Dawa or the Triple Blessed festival, Buddha Jayanti, Dzam Ling Chi Sam or the 'Deity Day', Tshechu marking the birth anniversary of Guru Padmasambhava in the month of July and Ngenpa GuDzom observed to ward off the evil spirits in December. All these are celebrated by the Tibetan Buddhist community of North Bengal with great fervor. It is a fascinating show of the traditional music, dance, costumes, jewellery and culinary of the Buddhist communities there.

In their paper, "Enhancing Buddhist Tourism in India: An Exploratory Study", Madhu Agarwal, Himanshu Choudhary and Gaurav Tripathi mentioned of a survey conducted by them where respondents were asked to indicate among a list of persons and places provided, those they felt they could associate the most with Buddhism. In that study, they found that "About 12.5 per cent of foreigners selected both Gautama Buddha and India as the person and place most associated with Buddhism whereas 39 per cent selected both Dalai Lama and Tibet as the person and place they associate with Buddhism. Also, 41 per cent of foreigners selected Gautama Buddha as the person most associated with Buddhism but only 17 per cent selected India as mentioned above." (Agarwal *et al.* www.emeraldinsight.com/1755-4217.htm). The study shows that India, despite being the birth place of the Buddha Himself, is lesser known as a country related to Buddhism than

Tibet. The popularity of Dalai Lama and Tibetan culture is easily fathomed from the findings of this survey. In this context the importance of the North Bengal in Buddhist tourism sector of our country becomes evident since the glimpse of the Tibetan Buddhism, its monastic life and popular culture along with that of other ethnic communities like Gorkhas and Lepchas that one may experience here can be a major factor in drawing both the domestic as well as the international tourists, as Dr. KarubakiDatta says, “Existence of these different schools are the legacy of the different phases of history of the region and that of the religion itself. The variations in rituals and practices add to the cultural diversity of the state...” (Datta, p. 1). The majestic view of the Himalayas gives an added impetus to the nature lovers too. In all, it may be said that in view of the fact that cultural diversity motivates the maximum number of tourists as reported by the International Passenger Survey mentioned above, the potential of North Bengal in respect to the religious cum cultural tourism as a major part of the Buddhist tourism as a whole cannot be exaggerated.

(b) Archaeo-heritage tourism:

Archaeological tourism as a significant part of heritage tourism is gaining popularity among tourists throughout the world. On the occasion of a conference named ‘Tourism at World Heritage Sites: Challenges and Opportunities’ held in Cesme (Izmir), Turkey in March 2013, in conjunction with the 55th Meeting of the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) a book named exactly after the theme of that conference was published by the UNWTO in 2015 where it was declared that “Such sites have an immeasurable inherent value in the expression and sense of identity of a host community. They play an important role in public education, and when managed properly, help to protect natural and cultural values and improve the quality of life for residents and visitors alike.” (<https://www.unwto.org/archive/global/publication/tourism-world-heritage-sits-challenges-and-opportunities>). There are a lot many benefits of combining archaeology with tourism in respect of proper preservation and conservation of the sites and the monuments, imparting historical and

archaeological knowledge to the common people and thus sensitizing them toward the material and moral value of the heritage, building a self-identity of the local community and recognizing their cultural resources, contributing to mutual respect and understanding between the guest and the host communities leading to a peaceful dialogue among varied cultures of different countries or the different regions within the same country. The proper promotion and development of the archaeo-tourism can display the soft power of a country, especially in a world where people are globally connected with each other. It is not that the Government of India is lagging behind to tap the potential of Buddhist tourism in this context, but what is unfortunate is that there is no such initiative that may be called an archaeological tourism in the state of West Bengal with regard to the Buddhist sites in spite of excavation of some major Buddhist structures that speak for the glory of the bygone days when the land was abounding with Buddhist monasteries and educational centres. Bengal was under the Buddhist Pala rule from 8th to 12th century AD. Both Fa-Hien and Hiuen-Tsang in their memoirs reported that they noticed a good many monasteries or Sangharamas with large aggregation of monks in some parts of Bengal. Hiuen-Tsang also mentioned a Stupa built by Ashokaraja by the side of the city of Tamralipta. The archaeological excavations have revealed only a small bit of material proof of these literary sources. Let us have a brief survey of the Buddhist spots of historical cum archaeological importance lying in different corners of West Bengal.

Moghalmari (SribandakaVihara): Located at Dantan-1 Block in the district of PashchimMedinipur it is 63 km away from the Kharagpur railway station via NH 16. The Department of Archaeology of the University of Calcutta conducted a six-phased excavation from 2003 to 2012 and the largest monastery complex of West Bengal was found underneath a mound called ‘SakhisonarDhipi’. The love story of Sakhisona, daughter of King Bikramakeshari, and Ahimanik, son of one of his ministers is a popular theme of the folklore here and there are traces of this legend scattered in different places of the adjacent areas like Jhargram and Nayagram. The name ‘Dantan’ itself has its own history. It is believed to be the ancient ‘Dandabhukti’ under the reign of the Gauda King

Shashanka which was mentioned by Sandhyakar Nandi in his Ramacharitam. The legend also has it that the place 'Dantan' derived its name from the tooth relic of the Buddha which might have been preserved here for some time before it was transported to Srilanka.

The discovery of the SribandakaVihara in Moghalmari has created quite a stir among the archaeologists and historians since it is believed to be one of the prominent monasteries seen by the Chinese pilgrim Hiuen-Tsang in the 7th century AD. Built in two structural phases (the first being 6th-7th centuries AD and the next being 11th-12th century AD) it has a Tri-ratha architecture. Beautiful stucco works all over the walls and use of around 45 types of decorative bricks resemble with the construction design of the famous Nalanda Mahavihara and partly with that of the RaktamrittikaMahavihara (<https://pashchimmedinipur.gov.in>). This Vihara was also found to be similar with the SomapuraMahavihara of Paharpur which was founded in the 8th-9th century and was largely influenced by the art and architecture of the former (Das *et al.*, p.59). The historical value of SribandakaVihara is fathomable from the recognition of the SomapuraVihara as a World Heritage Site by UNESCO.

This monastery at Moghalmari is also known to be situated at the vicinity of the ancient Tamralipta port and had connection with the trade route extending to Pataliputra, the major centre of commercial importance at that time along with places of Odissa which were connected with each other through an inland trade route as well. The discovery of Moghalmari monastery may reveal an interesting chapter of Indian trade and commerce through the inland and sea route of Bengal.

The excavation conducted in 2012 unearthed votive tablets with figures of the Buddha, Bodhisattvas and Buddhist inscriptions. The figures of Jambala and Buddhist Saraswati revealed by the archaeologists suggest that this Vihara was probably constructed in an era when Vajrayana Buddhism was actively practiced in Bengal. After the Directorate of Archaeology and Museums of the Government of West Bengal took over the charge of excavation and conservation of the Moghalmari site, a two-day Buddhist festival cum seminar was arranged by the Bauddha

Dharmankura Sabha on 24-25th January, 2016 there inviting monks from different corners of the country for special prayer and meditation. It was a pleasant co-incidence as some 40 artefacts including bronze statuettes measuring 7cm to 20-25 cm in height and 6-12 cm in width were tumbled out during the festival increasing the charm and fervor among the archaeologists, locals and the invited monastic congregation present there.

Some of the artefacts surfaced during excavation work at Moghalmari are preserved in the State Archaeological Museum situated on Satyen Roy Road in Behala. A local museum named DantapurPratnaSangrahashala is also there inside Dantan Social Club and Public Library known as the Town Library with a considerable number of artefacts unearthed from the site. SahityabinodLalit Mohan Samanta took the initiative to involve the local people with the preservation work of this historic landmark.

Details of Tourist Spot:

District Head Quarter- Medinipur

Nearest railway station- Belda/ Nekurseni

Nearest highway- NH 60

Nearest town: Kharagpur

Nearby accommodation- IIT Kharagpur Guest House, Debra Pathasathi

Jagjivanpur (NanadadirghikaUdrangaVihara): Before the excavation at Moghalmari it was the NandadirghiVihara of Jagjivanpur located 36 km east of Malda town at Habibpur Block in the district of Malda that held the most important position among the Buddhist sites in West Bengal. An accidental surfacing of a copper plate inscription of a hitherto unknown Pala King, Mahendrapaladeva of 9th century AD from a mound called Tulabhita led to the excavation of a huge monastery covering an area of nearly 9432 sq. m. According to the researchers, “The ground plan of the monastery resembles with the world-famous NalandaMahavihar while the sculptural

pattern is the manifestation of post-Gupta art of India” (Das *et al.*, p. 56; 2022). A large number of terracotta plaques along with seals and sealings have been unearthed from the mounds which are popularly known as Bhita or Danga in this region. Among the significant finds there are a plaque with a sacred text written on it and a bronze image of Marichi dating back to 9th-10th century AD. The Vihara possibly derived its name from a tank called Nandadighisituated in that location. The artifacts found from this site are preserved in the State Archaeological Museum at Behala as well as in the Malda Museum under the Directorate of Archaeology and Museums of the Government of West Bengal. Malda Museum is situated on Subhankar Bandh Road at Mokdampur.

Details of Tourist Spot:

District HeadQuarter- Malda town

Nearest railway station- Malda Town railway station

Nearest Highway- NH 12/ SH 10

Nearest town- Malda

Nearby accommodation- Amrapali Tourism Property (formerly Malda Tourist Lodge)

Karnasuvarna (RaktamrittikaMahavihara): The Department of Archaeology of the University of Calcutta conducted an excavation at Rajbaridanga in Murshidabad and a Buddhist monasterial structure covering an area of around 25 acres had been revealed on the left bank of the river Bhagirathi. Being founded in the 5th century AD it was older than the Nalanda Mahavihara and was a centre of Buddhist education as well. It may be mentioned here that the site has been affected by the multiple floods and shifting of the river course since 8th century AD (Das *et al.*, p. 61). The interesting fact about this monastery is that the excavations were made based upon an assumption that the name ‘Kia-lo-na-su-fa-la-na’ and ‘Lo-to-wei-chi’ mentioned in Hiuen-Tsang’s account

suggest Karnasuvarna and Raktamrittika respectively. As observed by Niyogi, “Hiuen-tsang ...visited Karnasuvarna...where he saw ten or more sangharamas with 2000 priests; they were followers of Hinayana of the Sammatiya school” (Niyogi, 2016, p. 70). Despite bearing the trace of a fabulous history of Bengal the regrettable condition of the site at present is a proof of our general negligence towards the rich heritage that has been passed down to us by our ancestors. The immense gap between the potential and the actualization of Buddhist tourism here is a matter of sheer disappointment for anyone concerned with this field.

Details of Tourist Spot:

District Head Quarter-Berhampore

Nearest railway station-Sargachi/Chiruti railway station

Nearest highway-NH 34

Nearest town-Berhamore

Nearest accommodation- There are hotels nearby with lodging facilities

Subarnavihar: The MouzaSubranabihar in Nadia District probably derived its name from the ruins of a Buddhist Stupa found here. There is an ASI listed historical site named Ballalddhibi around 5 km away from Subarnavihar. The Buddhist monastery covering an area of nearly 13,000 sq. m. was built during 11th-12th century AD and resembles with the structural pattern ofVikramshilaVihara and Somapura Vihara. As documented by the ASI, Kolkata Circle, “During 1982 to 1988, Kolkata Circle excavated the Mound and exposed huge brick structures and various antiquities datable to c. 10th to 12th cent. AD. The brick structure includes shrines on sides and a massive construction within an enclosure. Amongst the antiquities stucco heads possibly of Buddhist affiliation and copper objects used in religious purpose are noteworthy.”

(<https://www.asikolkata.in/nadia.aspx>). This Monument of national importance can be an ideal destination for a winter day out for the tourists.

Details of Tourist Spot:

District Head Quarter- Krishnanagar

Nearest railway station-Krishnanagar railway station

Nearest highway- NH 34

Nearest town-Krishnanagar

Nearest accommodation- Krishnanagar Municipal Tourist Lodge

Bharatpur Monastery: This Buddhist site in PurbaBardhaman district was excavated by the Kolkata Circle of the ASI in collaboration with the Bardhaman University during 1972-1975 and a large Buddhist Stupa along with a monasterial complex was found from here. Besides, among the significant findings there are black and red ware pottery from the Chalcolithic or Copper age and five miniature sculptures of seated Buddha in Bhumisparsha Mudra (earth-touching posture) which were probably used to be worshipped in the monastery. Covering a base area of nearly 13 sq. m. this Stupa was built during the Pala dynasty following the Pancharathastyle. While only smaller votive Stupas were unearthed from other major Buddhist sites of West Bengal the surfacing of this huge Stupa may tell an interesting story to us. Research reveals that “The surviving massive structure of the stupa-base indicates that the monumental height of the total body of the stupa including its presumably hemispherical dome used to create a powerful visual impact in the mind of the viewers. The stupa standing against the backdrop of vast lush green agrarian field on the bank of the mighty river Damodar created a contrasting visual relationship in ancient period...Situating in this cultural context of expansion of agriculture and rural settlements, Buddhist establishment of Bharatpur might have played significant role in the nexus between the

culturally vibrant urban centre of Karnasuvarna situating on the flood plain of the Bhagirathi in the present day Murshidabad district, the port city of Tamralipti in PurvaMedinipur district and the culturally peripheral forest covered Chhotanagpur upland on the western frontier of Bardhaman district.” (Majumdar, pp. 62-63; 2020).

Details of Tourist Spot:

District Head Quarter-Bardhaman town

Nearest railway station-Panagarh railway station

Nearest highway-NH 19

Nearest town-Panagarh

Nearest accommodation- BardhamanBhavan

Bangarh (DevikotVihara): The excavations during 1938-1941 conducted by the University of Calcutta on the eastern bank of the river Punarbhaba in the district of South Dinajpur revealed the curious site of Bangarh which is rich in historical as well as mythological value. The northern region of Bengal was under the rule of the Maurya dynasty in the 3rd century B.C. Later artefacts dating back to Sunga, Kushana, Gupta and Pala were found from this ancient place which was also known as Kotivarsha and believed to be the seat of the mythological demon king Bana. According to Puspa Niyogi, “The ruins of a vihara were found at Devikot (medieval Diw-kot), modern Bangarh in the Dinajpur district. This local monastery earned a reputation through its association with well known scholars, chief among them being Atulya-vajra (Advarajavajra), Avadhutapada, Udhilipa and Mekhala.” (Niyogi,p. 68; 2016). As per the report of The Telegraph dating 13.05.09, the ASI has a plan to build a museum along with a garden to showcase the artefacts found from this site. As the report goes, “The district magistrate said the revelation would bring

historians and researchers to the area and boost the tourism potential. The secretary of the Bangarh Archaeology Society, Partha Sarathi Moitra, said...“It shows that the entire area has a number of places of historical and mythological importance. If all these areas are developed, it will be a tourist circuit.” (‘Eight eras of Indian history unearthed in Bangarh’; <https://www.telegraphindia.com>). Some of the collections recovered during excavations, however, are preserved in the College Museum of Balurghat and Shibbati Missionary School.

Details of Tourist Spot:

District Head Quarter- Balurghat

Nearest railway station-Balurghat railway station

Nearest highway-NH 512

Nearest town-Balurghat

Nearest accommodation- Balurghat Circuit House

Bhot Bagan Moth:Ghusuri under the Salkia Municipalityin Howrah houses the first Tibetan monastery in the plainland built in 1776 AD as a result of the initiative taken by the third Panchen Lama, Lobsang Palden Yeshe with the noble objective of restoring the lost Indo-Tibet relationship as it was in the 11th-13th century. After Bogle conveyed his aspiration to Lord Warren Hastings, the then Governor-General of Bengal,he sanctioned 30 bighas of land at Ghusuri to this cause. Panchen Lama appointed a Hindu Dashnami monk called PurangiriGossain as a go between himself and the East India Company. Right from its inception it had a mixed religious character since it had Mahakala as its principal deity, idols of Goddess Tara, Cakrasamvara with His consort, VakraBhrukuti, Padmapani and other esoteric Gods and Goddesses most of which were brought from Tibet besides Shiva Linga which was most probably worshipped by Purangiri. Later the Shaiva rituals took over the entire monastery and it lost its Tibetan Buddhist nature. It is listed

under the West Bengal Heritage Commission (https://wbhc.in.>home>place_details). But this unique Buddhist monastery is entangled into legal disputes at present and suffering from lack of proper conservational measures that it deserves.

Details of Tourist Spot:

District Head Quarter- Howrah city

Nearest railway station- Liluah railway station

Nearest highway- G T Road

Nearest town- Salkia

Nearest accommodation- Rupmonjari Tourism Property of WBTDC

Apart from the above-mentioned sites, excavations at Tilpi and Dosa at Kodalia in South 24 Parganas revealed ruins of Buddhist structures which resemble with the description of Fa Hien. It is located near another important archaeological site of Chandraketugarh. Artifacts found from here are displayed in the State Archaeological Museum at Behala.

Kolkata and its suburban areas have a number of important Buddhist monasteries. Let us take a bird's eye view of the most notable ones:

BauddhaDharmankur Sabha or the Bengal Buddhist Association-Venerable KripasaranMahasthavir founded BauddhaDharmankur Sabha in 1892 with the noble intention of resurrecting Buddhism in India. It is “a socio-religious-cultural and philanthropic organization” as it is described in its official website (<https://bauddhadharmankursabha.in>). It has its branches all over the country. A journal named ‘Jagajyoti’ is published by the Sabha since 1908 and Buddhist scholars like GunalankarMahasthavir, ShilanandaBrahmachari, Prof. Dipak Kumar Barua and

Hemendu Bikash Chowdhury have discharged the function of editorship of this journal at different times. Located in Bowbazar area it offers modest accommodation to the students, researchers and tourists.

Mahabodhi Society of India- Founded by Anagarika Dharmapala in 1891 originally in Ceylone it has its headquarter at College Square in Kolkata. The foundation stone of Sri DharmarajikaChetiyaVihara was laid here in 1918. “In 1916, the Government of India agreed to offer the Maha Bodhi Society a sacred holy relic of the Buddha which had been discovered during the excavations at Bhattiprolu stupa in Madras Presidency provided the Society erected a suitable Vihara in Calcutta.” (<https://mbsiindia.org>). This holy tooth relic is displayed to the common people on the auspicious occasion of the Buddha Purnima every year. The society has its branches in Bhubaneshwar, Bodh Gaya, Sarnath, Lucknow, Shravasti, New Delhi and Lumbini. It provides educational, medical and relief services to people.

NipponzanMyohoji Buddhist Temple- Located in Dhakuria this Buddhist temple was founded by NichidatsuFujii, a Japanese monk in 1935.

Calcutta Karma Gon Buddhist Monastery- Located in Padmapukur area at Ballygunge, it was founded by a Buddhist monk named Akka Dorje of the Kagyu order who originally hailed from Darjeeling’s Bhutia Busti. It is a peaceful place where festivals are observed on special days of Tibetan Buddhism throughout the year.

Besides, mentions may be made of Myanmar Buddhist Temple on Central Avenue, Chinese Buddhist Temple on Jessore Road and FoGuang Shan Budddhist Temple at Tangra. The diverse schools of Buddhism that are represented in the city of Kolkata itself speak of the religious and cultural wealth that may be explored in a single day’s Buddhist heritage tour across the city. Many private agencies are conducting heritage walk within Kolkata, but very few of them have a Buddhist heritage walk through the city in their schedule.

(2) Limitations and Challenges

The Tourism Department of West Bengal Government, however, has a religious and pilgrimage tour programme within which there is a provision of exploring the Buddhist trail (<https://www.bengaltourism.in>). There is a special programme of the West Bengal Government named ‘The Journey of Insights’ involving twenty major Buddhist destinations including the Indian Museum across the state. The Department of Tourism has also launched an initiative under the name of ‘MahaPunyabhumiMahaTirthabhumi’ where it states that “The recent surge in religious tourism has encouraged the State Government to consider development of religious places either as a single destination or in combination of two or more such destinations in the form of a Circuit and promote tourism thereby facilitating tourists to explore the area and thus create awareness of humanity, heritage and preservation.” (<https://www.bengaltourism.in>). This circuit includes active Buddhist monasteries of the North Bengal, archaeological sites of Bangarh, Moghalmari and Jagjivanpur among the Buddhist tourist spots. But as rightly pointed out by Das *et al.* in their paper, “...pilgrimage tourism...is intermediate between religious tourism and pure pilgrimage, thereby demands a better understanding of the Buddhist heritage in terms of history, culture and aesthetics.” (Das *et al.* p. 62; 2022). Showcasing places of archaeological and historical importance as merely holy places and keeping them in the same bracket with other places which are strictly ‘religious’ in nature may affect their heritage value while designing a separate tourist circuit for the Buddhist spots which are significant in terms of pilgrimage, heritage and culture alike may attract both the pilgrims and the secular tourists including students and researchers.

The declared function of the Directorate of Archaeology and Museums under the Department of Information and Cultural Affairs of the Government of West Bengal as stated in their official website is “The Directorate of Archaeology and Museum has been perpetual with its untiring

efforts to unearth our hidden historical treasures, to preserve and proudly present our roots to the people of the world.” (<http://wb.gov.in/departments-details.aspx?id=D17110454524399&page=Information-&-Cultural-Affairs>). But what is regrettable is that places like Karnasubarna or SubarnaVihara which have immense historical value are excluded from the entire tour plan conceived by the Tourism department as has been mentioned above. Neither there is any Government Museum nor a proper Government accommodation in the vicinity of any of these important sites. The local people, except for a very few exceptions, are mostly ignorant about or indifferent to the cultural and historical value of these places.

It is generally seen that heritage sites with no tourism initiatives face plunder and adverse weathering and thus recede into oblivion. Tourism is a major means to generate employment opportunities involving myriad sectors like hospitality, transport, banking, local craftsmanship, food industries etc. The past glory gives a separate identity to the local commune and as a result of evolving business and work opportunities they actively take part in conservation of the heritage spots. The book titled ‘Tourism at World Heritage Sites: Challenges and Opportunities’ published by the UNWTO puts it thus: “Tourism means jobs, business opportunities for small and medium enterprises, the renewal of urban and rural areas and, when properly managed, the preservation and promotion of a country’s natural and cultural heritage. Tourism is one of the world’s largest and fastest-growing industries, and culture is one of the fastest developing components of international tourism. Since cultural exchange creates mutual understanding between different peoples and societies, cultural tourism is significant for contributing to mutual respect, peace, dialogue and diversity throughout the world.” (<https://www.unwto.org/archive/global/publication/tourism-world-heritage-sites-challenges-and-opportunities>).

On the one hand it is seen that the Government of India is all set to take full advantage of the Buddhist sites that evince for what an incredible past India is proud of, on the other, the remarkable

sites and monasteries of West Bengal which bear the legacy of a rich history of the respective regions and the later phase of Buddhism itself are woefully neglected without a proper initiative to display them to the world. The main factors which are holding the tourism facilities in these regions back may be jotted down in the following way:

- a) Lack of an integrated approach between the conservational agency and the tourism sector
- b) Lack of communication and cooperation between stakeholders at central and state levels
- c) Insufficiency of excavational measures taken towards continued revelation of the hidden treasures
- d) Paucity of measures taken towards the preservation and conservation of the excavated portions of the heritage sites
- e) Lack of imparting knowledge regarding correct interpretation of the sites
- f) Negligible advertising and publicizing of the cultural and heritage value of the sites
- g) Poor communication and transport facilities
- h) Lack of tourist facilities and amenities
- i) Lack of knowledgeable and informed guides at the tourist spots
- j) Lack of museums adjacent to the sites
- k) Lack of proper planning to create places of amusements for the tourists
- l) Poor sanitation, lack of cleanliness and security issues

As tourism has a major role to play in a labor-intensive country like India, the challenges that are obstructing the growth of this sector should be urgently addressed and a holistic planning should be adopted which is systematic, pragmatic, environment friendly and pro-people in nature.

(3) Recommendations and Suggestions

In the meeting of the G20 Tourism Working Group's meeting in collaboration of UNWTO and International Labour Organization (ILO) held in Gujarat from 7-9th February, 2023 focus was given on rural and archaeological tourism with five priority areas, namely, Green Tourism (eco-friendly tourism practices for a sustainable and responsible tourism), Digitalization (making use of digital technology for promotion of tourism sector), Skills (empowering the youth with an aim to generate employment opportunities), Tourism MSMEs (encouraging tourism based MSMEs, startups and entrepreneurship) and Destination Management (redesigning the strategic management of the tourist destinations to vitalize a holistic approach towards tourism). (<https://pib.gov.in/PressReleaseframePage.aspx?PRID=1896741>). This basic outline of the entire three-day meet speaks a lot about what to adopt as a sustainable and state of the art tourism policy if it has to thrive in the global tourism scenario. Taking lessons from what we understand to be the limitations and challenges discussed above, the following recommendations may be made keeping in line with the national cum global concerns in making tourism a unique tool of all-round development of a society in terms of its economy, self-esteem, infrastructural improvement, promotion of education, skill development and environmental sustainability:

- a) First and foremost, it is to be remembered that a certain level of sensitivity and caution should be undertaken while planning promotional measures for the tourist sites like Bharatpur or Bhot Bagan Moth, because it is never to be forgotten that these places are not only places of historical importance, but of religious importance as well and therefore, these are not to be looked upon as tourism commodities as such. Issues of commodification of holy Buddhist sites are to be dealt with responsibly and with additional care. In this connection we may take note of the 'Plan for Developing Tourism around Dantan' submitted to the DM of PashchimMedinipur on behalf of Bhattar College, Dantan. There Mr. Tarun Tapas Mukherjee suggested to erect a building at Moghalmari comprising "an advanced Tourist Lodge and Information Centre and a Museum and a Research Centre". He proposed that "The entire building needs to be designed following the structure of a

Buddhist Stupa” and also to name the Museum as “Dandabhukti Museum following the name of the ancient province of Bengal.” (Pradhan *et al*, p. 13) In support of his view he further clarified that “The name Dandabhukti prefixed to the museum will add more value to an ancient entity and indirectly add more substance to the tourism possibilities of the place.” (Pradhan and Mishra. p.14; 2020). This may be considered an ideal plan to rejuvenate the tourism value of a heritage place by way of making arrangements for modern amenities for the tourists keeping its core essence or holy nature intact. While planning to provide amusement facilities for the tourists it may be thought of to build a meditation centre and a path for the meditative perambulation (Chankramana) for the meditators along a beautifully decorated peaceful garden or lake. The natural resources available nearby can be utilized without going for expensive extravagances brought from outside.

- b) Green tourism should be encouraged in order to reach the global standards of it to make the foreign visitors feel at home. Restrictions on use of plastic, use of battery-run or electric vehicles at the compound, adoption of an eco-friendly waste management plan, non-harming local flora and fauna and promotion of local food are some of the measures that may be undertaken to strike a balance between economic and environmental well-being.
- c) Museums with artefacts found from the respective sites are essential so as to give a clear glimpse of the nature and antiquity of the spot to the tourists.
- d) It is important to train the local youth to serve as the informed guides of the spot because they are generally well versed with the regional history of that area including myths and folklores and thus have the potential to give a holistic picture of the site to the tourists. For example, besides the glorious Buddhist past of the Moghalmari monastery, the guide should narrate the local stories about Sakhisona after whom the mound was named and it will add the flavour of regional culture and popular narratives to the grand history of

evolution of Buddhism in Bengal. The guides, however, should be eloquent at least in Bengali, Hindi and English.

- e) Brochures and guide books with coloured photos of the site should be available at the museums which may be bought by the tourists if they wish so.
- f) Emphasis should be given on developing the transport and communication facilities. Poor communication and road condition are factors that discourage the tourists to explore new places. There should be signages at the important junctions of national and state highways to indicate the location and direction thereof.
- g) Accommodation with state of the art facilities along with multi-cuisine restaurants are a must to encourage the domestic as well as the overseas tourists to come over to the tourist spots and experience a comfortable stay there.
- h) Small shops or boutiques having good collection of the local art and crafts multiplies the attraction of a tourist spot providing the tourists the opportunity to fetch souvenirs for their loved ones and thus boost up the local craftsmanship of the area.
- i) Cleanliness and security issues should be addressed with utmost sincerity since these are sometimes found to be the primary concerns for the foreigners while visiting tourist spots in India. Clean public toilets and health centres are required.
- j) The virtual platform and the soft technology should be made full use of for advertising of the Buddhist sites in Bengal. Updated websites with detailed information along with online tickets and booking facilities should be there.
- k) With these aims in mind a PPP model may be followed involving the Government and private agencies or trusts to work in coherence with each other as a common stakeholder so that policies taken in the ministerial level are implemented and maintained in the ground level with the active participation from the local people who will show a spontaneous effort in preservation of the heritage site or the monument. It is very important for the heritage and tourism authorities to join hands. Sufficient investment in conservational fields and

aggressive marketing strategies should be taken up to generate awareness about the Buddhist sites in West Bengal.

Conclusion

It is imperative for the state of West Bengal, therefore, to emphasize on the management and presentation of its rich Buddhist heritage in order that its full potential of the religio-cultural and archaeo-heritage tourism may be exploited, thereby making way for a all round development of the state in terms of employment and entrepreneurship, infrastructure and education. It is our solemn duty too to pass on the legacy of our glorious past to the future generations of the country.

Reference

Afkhani Behrouz, (2021), 'Archaeological tourism; characteristics and functions', *Journal of Historical Archaeology and Anthropological Sciences*, Vol. 6, Issue 2-2021.

Agarwal Madhu *et al.*, 'Enhancing Buddhist tourism in India: an exploratory study', www.emeraldinsight.com/1755-4217.htm

Barua Dipak Kumar, (1969), *Viharas in Ancient India: A Survey of Buddhist Monasteries*, Indian Publication, Calcutta.

Chowdhury Madhusree, 'Buddhism- The Golden Heritage of Bengal',
<https://www.buddhistdoor.net/features/buddhism-the-golden-heritage-of-bengal/>
retrieved on 15.05.24

Das Bhaskar *et al.*, (2022), 'A Study on the Ruins of Buddhist Monasteries in West Bengal in the Context of Buddhist Tourism Development', *Indian Journal of Geography & Environment*, 19 (2022), April, 2022, Vidyasagar University, ISSN: 0972-7388,
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/363539472_A_Study_on_the_Ruins_of_Buddhist_Monasteries_in_West_Bengal_in_the_Context_of_Buddhist_Tourism_Development
retrieved on 25.05.24

DattaKarubaki, 'Buddhists and Buddhist Legacies in Modern Bengal', *Karatoya: NBU J. Hist. Vol. 10*, ISSN: 2229-4880

Dipananda BD, 'Buddhist Tourism in West Bengal and Bangladesh: An Untapped Resource', *Buddhistdoor Global*, 2018-01-30.

Eight eras of Indian history unearthed in Bangarh', *The Telegraph*, Thursday, May 14, 2009.

Furui Ryosuke, 'Buddhist Viharas in Early Medieval Bengal: Organizational Development and Historical Context', *Buddhism, Law and Society*, 2023, 7 (2021-2022), hal-04100180

'How the Archaeological Survey of India is transforming tourism domain', *Travel World, The Economic Times*,

<https://travel.economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/destination/states/how-the-archaeological-survey-of-india-is-transforming-tourism-domain/99730258> retrieved on 25.5.24.

‘India to showcase success in rural and archaeological tourism at G-20 meeting’, *The Hindu*, 4 February, 2023.

MajumdarSomreeta, ‘What is in The Location: A Geo-archaeological Study of the Landscape of the Buddhist Monasteries of Western Bengal’, *International Journal of Historical Insight and Research*, Vol. 5, No. 4, Oct-Dec, 2019.

MajumdarSomreeta, ‘Locating the Monastery in Landscape Context: A Preliminary Study of RaktamrittikaMahavihara of Karnasuvarna’, *Heritage: Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies in Archaeology* 7 (2019): 622-641.

MajumdarSomreeta, ‘Archaeological Landscape of The Buddhist Stupa of Bharatpur’ *Arnava*, Vol. 9, No. 2, Half Yearly, Year 2020 ISSN: 2320-0103

Niyogi Puspa, (2016), *Buddhism in Ancient Bengal*, Mahabodhi Book Agency, Kolkata.

Pradhan Bikram Chandra and Dr. Pabitra Kumar Mishra, A Plan for Developing Tourism around Dantan, Institutional-Distinctiveness-2020-21.pdf

‘Promotion of Buddhist Tourism Circuits in Selected Asian Countries’, (2003), ESCAP Tourism Review, No. 24, Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific, United Nations, New York.

Sharma M. P., ‘Indian Buddhist Tourism: Progress and Emerging Issues’, *Journal of Marketing Strategy*, Vol. 5, Issue 3, December 2017, ISSN: 2347-3770.

‘Tourism at World Heritage Sites: Challenges and Opportunities’,
<https://www.unwto.org/archive/global/publication/tourism-world-heritage-sites-challenges-and-opportunities>.

